

The Influence of Self-Regulatory Efficacy on Consumer Purchase Behavior of pirated Music CDs in Tanzania

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Dr. Hellenah Mohamedy Mushi ⁽²⁾ Prof Nor Azila Mohd Noor

Othman Yeop Abdullah - Graduate of Business School, Universiti Utara Malaysia

Abstract

The music industry generally has experienced an upsurge in the sales of pirated music CDs and especially in Tanzania. While this trend continues, very limited studies have been conducted in developing countries. This study is, therefore, one of the few attempts to investigate the influence of self-regulatory efficacy on the purchase behavior of consumers in Tanzania. The casual model was empirically tested by using partial least-square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). A survey of 491 Generation Y consumers as the main music users in Tanzania was carried out. This study was conducted using an intercept survey method at selected malls in a former capital city of Tanzania (Dar-es- salaam). The result reveals that self-regulatory efficacy positively influences purchase behavior among the selected respondents. Implications of the findings were presented.

Keywords: Pirated Music, Self-Regulatory Efficacy, Tanzania, Theory of Planned Behaviour

The music industry has experienced unprecedented levels of uncertainty and financial turmoil (Sinclair & Green, 2016). The International Federation of the Phonographic Industry (IFPI) reports that piracy has led to a 31 percent decline in recorded music sales between 2004 and 2010 and a potential retail loss of 240 billion euros from 2008 to 2015 in Europe (Ifpi, 2012). Similarly, the Recording Industry Association of America (RIAA) claims that there has been a decline of 47 percent in sales (RIAA, 2015). Music piracy has severely fragmented the advertising budget of the industry as it is expected to increase cost on R & D (Bartkus & Akulavicius, 2015). The consequences are not only economic for the music industry, but there also is a great number of job loses within music industries affected by music piracy (Adermon & Liang, 2014; Arli et al., 2015).

The problem is not related only to the manufacturers of pirated music. The demand

for these types of pirated music is a key element in the increase in purchases of pirated music CDs (Andersen & Frenz, 2010; Tat et al., 2012). Billions of dollars are lost annually due to music CDs piracy culprits originating prevalently from the Asia Pacific region (China, Hong Kong, South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Indonesia, Thailand and

Malaysia) since music piracy involve almost everything under the music industry ranging from purchasing CD's, copying CD's, buying downloads online, P2P file sharing, and streaming music (with or without video).

In Tanzania, the level of music piracy is high, especially for entertainment software. Sales of music CDs have continued to drop tremendously; for instance, production of music CDs for the past 10 years was 300 CDs per year but dropped to 100 CDs in 2015 and further declined by over 50% in both production and distribution of original audio products (CDs) in 2015 due to increased sales of fake CDs in the country (The Daily News dated 6 July 2015). For example, several newspapers had the following issues announced: "Tanzania: Over 65,000 Contraband Local, Foreign CDs, DVDs Confiscated" (The Daily News dated 3 June 2015); "Poor CD, DVD sales affect local film, music industries" (The Daily News dated 6 July 2015); "Substandard goods flood Tanzania market" (The Daily News dated 26 October 2013); and "Tanzania: Fake substandard goods pose a risk to local industries" (All Africa dated 23 May 2014).

In view of the above, the objective of this paper is to empirically consider one critical factor that

influences pirated music purchase behavior among Tanzanians.

Literature Review

Purchase Behavior

It is defined as an “individual’s readiness and willingness to purchase a certain brand or service” or “decision processes and consumer involvement in purchasing and using a brand” (Ajzen & Fishbein 1980). Simply, it is regarded as the purchasing of goods and services for personal consumption, and means of consumption through the process of buying or using the goods, or the amount that people buy or use (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2009), purchase behavior is evident when a consumer goes through all the relevant steps of the purchase. This would involve the brand, method of payment, package, location of purchase, and all the other factors related to purchasing a particular brand.

The aforementioned definition states that purchase behavior is the end step that results from the different processes that a consumer goes through. According to a study by Thackston, (2003) there are different stages in consumer purchasing behaviour, and these can be summarized as the need/desire to recognize brands, search for information about the brands that can complete the need, estimate the set of options presented in the market to purchase a brand, and the estimation of their decision after actual purchase. Consumers may make their purchases at several locations and at any time, but purchase behavior needs not to involve all the processes mentioned above.

Consumer buying behaviour is the process by which individuals search for, select, purchase, use, and dispose of goods and services, in satisfaction of their needs and wants (Bello, 2008). Along the same lines, music piracy is the copying and distributing of copies of a piece of music for which the composer, recording artist, or copyright record company did not give consent (Chiou et al., 2005). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2009), understanding purchase behaviour is therefore very important in order to attract and retain consumers. Thus,

marketers need to keep improving their understanding of consumer behaviour, both from an individual’s perspective and also in terms of market sectors.

Self-Regulatory Efficacy and Purchase Behaviour

In the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) framework, perceived behavioural control (PBC) also has a direct effect on actual behaviour. While PBC is not a new concept within the domain of modelling unethical decision making, researchers tended to limit the focus of PBC to its role in the formation of purchase intention (Carrington et al., 2010). The current study uses self-regulatory efficacy as perceived behaviour control to measure the direct link to actual behaviour. As such, previous scholars recommended further investigation to examine to what extent does the self-regulatory efficacy and actual behaviour is linked to each other (LaRose et al., 2003).

Despite of the fact that the role of self-regulatory efficacy on actual behaviour has been largely ignored in ethically questionable behaviour, it has been widely examined in relation to a wide diversity of other behaviour such as un (ethical) behaviour (Aarts & Dijksterhuis, 2000), marketing (Antonetti, 2013), unregulated internet usage behaviour (LaRose et al., 2003) and consumer behaviour (Baumeister et al., 2008). Caprara et al., (2002) for example examine the impact of perceived self-regulatory efficacy on violent conduct. This reduces the chance of violent actions (Loeber & Stouthamer-Loeber, 1998).

Hypothesis Development

Based on the above argument, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: Self-regulatory efficacy positively influences purchase behavior

Methodology

Quantitative research is used in this current study, and it is executed with the objective of achieving a good understanding of the purchase behavior of Tanzanian consumers of pirated music CDs.

This current study uses a cross-sectional method to answer the study's research hypothesis. The survey method was employed because survey research is the finest method to be applied in order to get personal and social facts, beliefs and attitudes (Kerlinger, 1973). The respondents are designated using probability sampling and a self-administered questionnaire, administered to all the respondents in selected shopping malls in the Dar-es-salaam City. The sampling design of simple random sampling was used, as it has the least bias and offers the most generalisability (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The unit of analysis for this study involved individual consumers aged 18 and above who go shopping at selected shopping malls in the Dar es- Salaam City.

The population for this study covered consumers who are 18 years and above and who live in Tanzania. The purpose of selecting only consumers in this age range is to ensure that all respondents have some knowledge, experience and intend to purchase pirated music CDs from various outlets so that they were able to answer the questionnaire accurately. Furthermore, for customers who are above 18 years of age, they were able to determine their piracy behaviour because they are matured enough to determine even their income. Specifically, the sample was based on consumers who went shopping at various shopping malls in the Dar-es-salaam City, Tanzania.

Additionally, based on their unique predilections of Generation Y, Djasmasbi et al., (2010) posited that future studies should identify and extend studies to other characteristics that might appeal to Generation Y. Therefore, this study focuses on Generation Y of Tanzania music piracy behaviour particularly in purchases of pirated music CDs. This segment of the society needs to be examined as they increase the purchase of pirated music CDs in Tanzania. Hence, they can generate the required sample for this type of survey.

Consequently, data were collected from Generation Y selected sample of 491 from various selected popular malls in Tanzania using mall intercept. Mall intercept has been employed by various marketing researchers and has been proved to be good for research of this nature (Grace & O'Cass, 2005).

The variables under investigation in this study are purchase behavior and self-regulatory efficacy. To measure these variables, items for self-regulatory efficacy were adapted from LaRose and Kim, (2007) while items for purchase behavior were adapted from Lee (2009) and Tat et al. (2012) based on Likert scale of 1-7. SPSS and SmartPLS were used to analyse the data. The SPSS was used for the preliminary analysis while PLSSEM was used for the measurement and structural model of the study.

Measurement Model

Under the measurement model in PLS SEM, researchers are required to establish individual item reliability, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. In establishing the item reliability, convergent reliability, and internal consistency reliability, it is suggested that researchers consider items loadings, composite reliability (CR) and average variance explained (AVE) (Hair et al., 2014). By standard, all the item loadings must not be less than 0.4, while CR and AVE must not be less than 0.70, and 0.50 respectively and which this study complied with.

Structural model

In the assessment of the structural model, the basic requirements are the establishment of path coefficient significance, determinant coefficient (R^2). Thus, this study applied the nonparametric evaluation criteria based on bootstrapping procedure with 5000 bootstrap samples and 491 cases to in order to assess the significance of the path coefficients (Hair et al., 2014). Although path coefficients are very important in PLS analysis, Hair et al., (2014) confirm that when paths are non-significant or reveal signs that are against the hypothesized direction, the prior hypotheses should be rejected. On the other hand, significant paths

showing the hypothesized direction support the proposed causal relationship empirically. Further, they state that each path coefficient's significance, just as with the indicators' weights and loadings, can be assessed by means of a bootstrapping procedure.

Moreover, the critical t-values for a one-tailed test must be over 2.33 (with a significance level of 1%), 1.645 (with a significance level of 5%), and 1.28 (with a significance level of 10%) (Wegner, 2010). Along this line, the researcher set 5,000 subsamples with a replacement number from the bootstrap cases equal to the original number of samples (491) in order to produce standard errors and obtain t-statistics. Table 1 contains the path coefficient and the bootstrapping results.

**Table 1:
Result of the Structural Model**

Hypotheses	b	SE	Tvalue	Pvalue	Decision
SRE → CPB	0.054	0.054	1.448**	0.074	Supported

Table 1 shows the assessment of the full model. Based on these results, the hypothesis is elaborated as follows: The relationship between self-regulatory efficacy and behaviour is significant as beta= 0.054, t-value of 1.448 and p value of 0.05 ($\beta = 0.054$, $t = 1.448$, $p < 0.05$).

Evaluation of Variance Explained in the Endogenous Latent Variables

According to PLS-SEM researchers (Hair et al., 2012, Hair et al. 2011; Henseler et al., 2009), another very important and commonly used criterion for assessing structural model is the coefficient of determination (R-squared value). This coefficient is a measure of the proportion of an endogenous latent construct's variance that is explained by one or more criterion construct (s). It measures a model's predictive accuracy and could be calculated as the squared correlation that exists between a specific endogenous construct's actual and predicted values (Elliott & Woodward, 2007; Hair et al., 2006; Hair et al., 2010). Thus, it is difficult to provide a rule of thumb for an acceptable R^2 value, as it varies across research disciplines and

dependent on the complexity of research models (Hair et al., 2014). In Table 2 R^2 value of the endogenous latent variable is presented.

Table 2
Coefficient Determinant

Latent Construct	Variance Explained (R^2)
Purchase Behaviour	20.1%

As shown in Table 2, this study's model explains 20.1% of the total variance in consumer purchase behaviour, suggesting that the exogenous latent constructs of self-regulatory efficacy explain only 20.1% of the variance of the endogenous latent construct-consumer purchase behaviour. Thus, going by the suggestions of Falk and Miller (1992) coefficient determinant (R^2) of 0.10 is acceptable as in the case of this study.

Discussion of findings

The finding of this study indicates that self-regulatory efficacy positively influences the purchase behaviour of pirated music CDs among Tanzanian consumers. The result was significant between self-regulatory efficacy and consumer buying behaviour. In the TPB framework, self-regulatory efficacy also has a direct result on consumer purchase behaviour. While self-regulatory efficacy is not a new notion within the domain of signifying unethical decision making, scholars tended to limit the emphasis on self-regulatory efficacy to its role in the formation of purchase (LaRose & Kim 2007). As such, many scholars were recommended for further investigation to examine to what extent does the self-regulatory efficacy and actual behaviour is linked to each other (Bandura et al., 2003; Caprara et al., 2002; LaRose et al., 2003).

Despite of the fact that the role of self-regulatory efficacy on actual behaviour has been largely ignored in ethically questionable behaviour, it has been widely examined in relation to a wide diversity of other behaviour such as usage and un (ethical) behaviour (Aarts & Dijksterhuis, 2000) marketing

(Sultan et al., 2012), unregulated internet usage behaviour LaRose et al., (2003), and consumer behaviour (Baumeister et al., 2008). Caprara et al., (2002) for example examine the impact of perceived self-regulatory efficacy on violent conduct, found that self-regulatory efficacy was a significant determinant of violent conduct in performance with communication with parents.

Baumeister et al., (2008) and Schmeichel, Gailliot, and Baumeister, (2005) in their study noted that the members with fewer self-regulatory properties were more likely to choose different and easier process, which leaves less of a memory trace than participants who had a full supply of self-regulatory properties. This is also supported by a study by Sultan et al., (2012) in US university that self-regulatory responsibilities lead to following decrements in self-control. On the other hand, the workplace deviance behaviour recognises the importance of self-regulatory efficacy in the incidence of unethical behaviours. Kura et al., (2014) found that employees who are high in self-regulatory efficacy are less likely to participate in organizational deviance because they are proficient of resisting the influence of situational aspects. Therefore, it may be inferred that, while self-regulatory efficacy is a significant determinant of purchases of pirated music CDs, the relational strength between self-regulatory efficacy and consumer purchase behaviour is still at a growing stage.

Self-regulatory efficacy is an important cognitive foundation that can motivate individual to abstain from engaging in deviant acts (Bandura, 1986; Caprara et al., 2002 & Kura et al., 2014). In general, most of the studies conducted in various settings to examine the relationship between self-regulatory efficacy and consumer purchasing behaviour have demonstrated a positive association between these two constructs. This indicates that people's perceptions of the capacity to resist temptation or pressures to performing the behaviour influenced their action. Thus, based on this inference, it is justifiable that self-regulatory efficacy is a significant determinant of purchase behaviour of pirated music CDs.

Implication of Study

The study followed a novel research framework modified from Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) that was originally proposed by Ajzen, (2006) to study purchase behaviour. Past investigations indicated that the model was hardly examined in explaining music piracy behaviour. A systematic literature exploration shows that the model went almost overlooked by music piracy behaviour researchers because it was not meant for explaining music piracy related behaviour. An enormous amount of past publications based on TPB was overwhelmingly linked to music piracy behaviour and digital piracy research. Further review of the literature indicated every possibility of using this model for music piracy behaviour research. The empirical evaluation of the model shows adequate fit statistics with sufficient level of statistical power. Therefore, the current study may have theoretically contributed to the body of knowledge by proposing and empirically examining the modified framework of TPB.

Second, the study focused on purchase behavior gap that is prevalent among consumers and identification of specific variables of self-regulatory efficacy has been viewed as a potential predictor of purchase actual behavior (Caprara et al., 2002), whereas only a few studies actually examined this variable under pirated music context (LaRose & Kim, 2007). This has also been the case in studies done under the Tanzania context. The empirical evaluation shows that the construct is significant in explaining purchase behavior, thereby added some effect in explaining the purchase-behavior gap. Therefore, inclusion and evaluation of self-regulatory efficacy in the model may be considered an important theoretical contribution.

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